

Impact of Social Media on the Mental Health of Youth

Lavneet Vashisth

Assistant Professor of Journalism and Mass Communication,
Mata Gujri College, Fatehgarh Sahib, Punjab, India Email: lavneet025@gmail.com

Received: 10/01/2025

1st BPR: 19/01/2025

2nd BPR: 02/02/2025

Accepted: 12/02/2025

Abstract

Today's world is of technology. Internet, or we can say, social media has acquired literally every sector. In this era of advancement, everyone is around social media. No matter what age group people belong to, everyone directly or indirectly is using or affected by social media. Particularly the youth is around social media like no one other & this frequent use of social media is affecting their minds, their behavior and their relations in so many ways. They don't even realize that the excessive use of social media has made its puppets. This research indicates that social media can result in depression, anxiety and relationships problems in youth.

This glorious world of social media is far-far darker. There are already many debates on the topic of benefits and drawbacks of social media. This study was conducted to investigate the impact of social media on young people's mental health. This study uses a random sampling strategy, and the survey method has been employed to provide fair and accurate data.

Introduction

Mental health, these days has become a very crucial topic to discuss about. It is a state of human well-being. But, this stressful life and world of hurry made humans so busy that they don't care about their mental pressure for a second & this social media worked as a cherry on the cake in this matter.

Social media has become a vital aspect of our lives in recent years. Every individual is around social media and especially the youth. Youngsters these days are more connected with social media and tend to socialise themselves more 'online' rather than 'offline'. In today's world of technology, it seems very difficult to live without phones, internet or social media. Social media has been designed in a way that everyone is forced to stay in connected with it. With every single scroll, you will get a new content which forces individuals to stay online for a long period of time. According to reports, Indians spend near about 194 minutes a day on social media platforms like Instagram, Snapchat, and Facebook etc. This means that every individual uses social media for near about 3 hours a day.

Social media has been used so extensively over the past few decades. So, it is crucial to examine how it affects mental health. Since more people are presenting with mental health symptoms like anxiety, sadness, low self-esteem, etc. as a result of our heavy reliance on social media, social media's impact on mental health makes it more difficult to provide social services on a micro level. It seems like it is becoming an addiction for most of the people. Youth these days are more present on social media rather than being present around their natural environment. This addiction of social media is making so many harmful impacts on the youth's mental & physical well-being.

In a recent study, it is found that many celebrities have also taken a break from social media for the sake of their mental health because of the toxicity present around. Although social media use has become a commonplace aspect of modern life, spending too much time on it can also have a detrimental effect on sleep patterns. Social media addiction can lead to excessive screen time that interferes with sleep. Furthermore, social media sites have the potential to foster a culture of comparison in which teens feel pressured to live up to the expectations set by their peers

According to a number of studies on the effects of social media, extended use of sites like Facebook, Instagram, and others may be linked to symptoms of stress, anxiety, and depression. A decrease in subjective well-being and life satisfaction, as well as an increase in loneliness and FOMO, have all been linked to excessive use of these social media platforms. Low self-esteem and depressive symptoms are common among users who are at risk of developing a social media addiction.

Undoubtedly, social media is a great medium. It provides everyone common platform to share their views, it helps people to connect, helps them grow their business and helps them get educated but social media has a dark side

too. Youngsters spent most of their time online. Hence, they consume what social media is serving them and even with the advancement of technology and introduction of AI (Artificial Intelligence) social media has also become a threat to everyone. Social media has no limit of content & individuals sometimes neglect that what kind of content they are consuming and what effect does this content is having on their minds directly or in-directly. With this study, I therefore attempted to contribute to the understanding of how social media affects the everyday lives and mental health of young people.

Objectives

The purpose of this study is to determine the reasons for the high usage of social media among young people. To study the emotions of children without the use of social media. To understand how social media affects young people's lifestyles. To research how relationships are affected by social media. To discover how social media affects people's behavior.

Hypothesis

Social media is primarily used by young people as a way to express their emotions and pass the time. After a period of not using social media, children experience loneliness. Young people's habits are influenced by social media content. Individuals are spending more time online, which can cause major issues in relationships. There are behavioral changes and other psychological issues that people often experience.

Methodology

In this research work, Quantitative Research Method with Survey Technique and Questionnaire as a tool, is used to collect the data. Data is collected from people using Simple Random Sampling method and sending out questionnaire. The results of which can be depicted in the form of numerical values.

Review of Literature

Kimberly Panganiban (2022) in the article social media & Relationships asserted that social media can affect relationships by reducing the quantity and calibre of time spent with partner. Whether we want it or not, social media does reduce the amount of time we spend in relationships, which can lower our sense of fulfilment and connection and eventually result in a social media addiction. Because of the high usage of social media, We find it much simpler to disparagingly compare our partner to other people or our relationship to other relationships. This may affect our dedication to our partnership, resulting in betrayal and potentially dissolution.

According to the News published in Dainik Bhaskar (2024) – Title (Celebrities are moving away from social media, Reason- Mental Health and Negativity) Agency New York- social media is a place where celebrities or film stars get a platform to reach out to their fans. However, every coin has two sides. While social media gives everyone an opportunity to connect with others but on the other hand using this for a huge amount of time, also harms one's mental peace. For this reason, many Hollywood celebrities have taken a break from social media. From famous singer Selena Gomez to John Legend and Billie Eilish, these are the stars who took a break from social media. However, Hollywood actor Tom Holland, singer Ed Sheeran, models Gigi Hadid and Nick Jonas, also took a break from social media in the past.

American singer John Legend decided to take a break from social media. He said, now the platform has become poisonous. To take care of my mental health, it is important for me to take a break from social media. I can't take care of my mental health without leaving social media. Captain America movie Actor Chris Evans, also took a break from social media a few months ago. He said that to focus on my health and myself, I have to take a break from social media. It is quite toxic.

The Social Dilemma: social media and Your Mental Health by McLean in January 2023 believes that at a time when teen bodies are changing, Facebook, Instagram, and Snapchat make it more likely that users will see filtered, unrealistic photos. It is simple to locate and use apps that offer the user airbrushing, and additional filters. Everyone looks flawless; it's not just celebrities. Teenagers may have a hard time telling what is real and what isn't because the digital world is filtered, which can be emotionally and physically taxing upon them.

In a June 2018 New York Times article, a newlywed couple almost split up after their honeymoon because the female partner spent more time planning the trip and sharing selfies than she did with her husband.

In their study, "Impact of Social Media on the Mental Health of Adolescents and Young Adults," Abderrahman M. Khalaf, Abdullah A. Alubied, Ahmed M. Khalaf, and Abdallah A. Rifaey (2023 Aug 5) reported that a recent study showed that 14.8% of young people were admitted to mental hospitals because they posed a risk to themselves or others due to the type of content available on social sites.

Melissa G. Hunt, a psychologist, wrote in *Feeling down? Social media may be to blame* (2023) that the less use of social media can reduce feelings of loneliness and depression.

Anwar Bisma (2022) in *The Correlation between social media and Mental Health* stated that Humans are social organisms by nature, and we need connections to keep our mental health in check. Research indicates that the more social media interactions you have instead of in-person interactions, can raise your risk of developing or exacerbating the symptoms of depression, anxiety, and other similar mood disorders. A new term, Snapchat dysmorphia, has been coined to describe the deeply ingrained desire to alter your physical features to fit filtered images, and it is used to describe a trend among young women who use social media filters. Feelings of dissatisfaction and unhappiness can arise as a result of social comparison. Research indicates that excessive use of social sites can lead to feelings of loneliness among students, worsening psychosocial well-being issues such as adjustment and self-esteem. The UK Mental Health Foundation reports that 60% of 18-34-year-olds feel lonely despite widespread access to online communication.

Sarah Nichole Koehler, Bobbie Rose Parrell (2020) *The impact of social media on mental health*, it was discovered that people who use social media may feel depressed, insecure, jealous, socially isolated, and low in self-esteem. When comparing their lives to the content of other users, some people experience cognitive distortions that can cause them to feel depressed and hopeless (Ashford, 2017).

Research Questions & Outcomes

Q.1 For how long do you use social media?

	Total 80	%age
Less than 1 hour	4	5%
For 1 to 2 hours	22	27.5%
More than 2 hours	26	32.5%
No time limit	28	35%

Q.2 Which platform do you prefer to use?

	Total 80	%age
Instagram	62	77.5%
Snapchat	4	5%
X or Twitter	1	1.25%
Facebook	2	2.5%

Q.3 Why do you use social media?

	Total 80	%age
For time pass	25	31.25%
For information	20	25%
For entertainment	14	17.5%
For chatting	13	16.25%

Q.4 According to you, at which extent you feel that social media is impacting your mental health?

	Total 80	%age
To large extent	14	17.5%
To some extent	45	56.25%
To less extent	21	26.25%

Q.5 At what extent you prefer using social media while feeling lonely or sad?

	Total 80	%age
To large extent	16	20%
To some extent	44	55%
To less extent	20	25%

Q.6 What kind of content you prefer to watch when you feel sad?

	Total 80	%age
Motivational	33	41.25%
Sad	8	10%
Comedy	32	40%
Romantic	7	8.75%

Q.7 Do you ever feel depressed or doubt yourself with the kind of content you get on your explore page?

	Total 80	%age
To large extent	9	11.25%
To some extent	42	52.5%
To less extent	29	36.25%

Q.8 Do you feel that social media is the first thing you use to express your feeling?

	Total 80	%age
To large extent	20	25%
To some extent	31	38.75%
To less extent	29	36.25%

Q.9 How do you like to spend your time more?

	Total 80	%age
By hanging out with friends	20	25%
On social media	32	40%
With family	18	22.5%
Other ways	10	12.5%

Q.10 Do you feel any kind of change in your behaviour because of the impact of social media?

	Total 80	%age
To large extent	37	46.25%
To some extent	25	31.25%
To less extent	18	22.5%

Q.11 Do you feel lonely when there is no internet or you don't use social media?

	Total 80	%age
To large extent	34	42.5%
To some extent	28	35%
To less extent	18	22.5%

Q.12 Do social media content make any kind of changes in your lifestyle or living habits?

	Total 80	%age
To large extent	19	23.75%
To some extent	47	58.75%
To less extent	14	17.5%

Q.13 Have you ever faced relationship problems because of social media?

	Total 80	%age
Yes	17	21.25%
Sometimes	28	35%
Never	35	43.75%

Q.14 Do you believe that social media is marking a huge impact on human behaviour?

	Total 80	%age
Yes, at some extent	49	61.25%
Moderate	22	27.5%
No, i don't think so	9	11.25%

Q.15 Do you agree with the fact that social media is killing relationships these days?

	Total 80	%age
Strongly Agree	38	47.5%
Agree	15	18.75%
To some extent	27	33.75%

Q.16. Do you feel that people try to show off their selves on social media platforms?

	Total 80	%age
To large extent	53	66.25%
To some extent	22	27.5%
To less extent	5	6.25%

Q.17 Do you feel that social media is the reason that most of the people always wants everything perfect and expect happy ending?

	Total 80	%age
To large extent	42	52.5%
To some extent	33	41.25%
To less extent	5	6.25%

Conclusion

The study "Impact of Social Media on the mental health of youth" provides significant and crucial findings. The main objectives of this study were to find out why youth use social media at such a large extent and to understand what youngsters feel without using social media. Also, to know about the living style of today's youth it is very important to understand the effect of social media on the lifestyle of youngsters. Social media today became a much-known platform for everyone to share their relationship status and personal/private life so it is necessary to study the effect of social media on the relationships. The last objective was to learn about the impact of social media on human behaviour.

The first hypothetical statement to be tested was that "Most of the youngsters use social media just to spend their time and to express their feelings." This hypothesis is proved right as the data reveals that 35% users use social media with no time limit and with this 31% of the respondents uses it just for time pass, 25% for informational purpose. In addition to expression of their feelings, 39% respondents said that they use social media at some extent to express their feelings as a second tool whereas 25% use it as the first medium to pour out their feelings.

Surprisingly, 40% respondents said that they like to spend their time on social media more whereas 25% choose to be with their friends and 22% with their family. This data simply reflects that today's youngsters use social media at a huge extent just to pass their time and even with no time limit. The data also presents that 40% of the respondents like to spend their time on social media rather than being with family or friends. In other words, we can also say that the youth these days are addicted to social media and are wasting their time on such platforms by using them for no productive purpose.

The second hypothetical statement to be tested was that "Youngsters feel lonely when they don't use social media." Data here proves the assumption right as a large number of respondents i.e., 43% said that they feel lonely at a large extent when there is no internet. This means that the youth have bounded their selves till social media only because they feel empty without it.

"Social media content influences youth and changes their habits" was the third hypothetical statement. According to the data, 59% of the respondents think that their lifestyle and living habits have changed as a result of social media material. To a lesser degree, however, 17% of respondents think social media has an impact. Furthermore, according to 66% of the respondents, people make a significant effort to showcase themselves on social networking platforms. This research unequivocally demonstrates how social media is pushing young people to alter their lifestyles and exalt others, which is detrimental to them and misleading to others.

The fourth hypothetical statement to be tested was that "People spend more time online which may lead to serious relationship problems." Data here proves that 40% of the youth like to spend their time on social media more whereas 25% choose to be with their friends and 22% with their family. Similarly, 47% of the respondents are strongly agreed with the fact that social media are killing relationships these days. With these findings, we can say that people are around social media more rather than including themselves in physical world and such kind of habits somewhere leads to relationship issues because youth may give more preference to their online relations and this may result in the demise of the relationship.

The fifth hypothetical statement was "A person tends to feel behavioural changes and has some other psychological problems." This hypothesis is proved right as the data reveals that 61% of the respondents believe that social media is marking a huge impact on human behaviour whereas 28% said that the effect is moderate. In addition, 54% respondents said that they feel depressed and even started doubting their selves at some extent with the kind of content they get online.

Surprisingly, 47% of youngsters believe that they feel change in their own behaviour because of the impact of social media. On the other hand, 56% of the respondents felt that social media is impacting their mental health at some extent. Not just this, 54% believes that social media is the reason that most of the people always wants everything perfect and expect happy ending. With all these findings, It is proved that social media is marking a huge impact on the minds of youth as they are addicted to it and even bounds their selves around social media only. Social media has also made a strong boundary for youth with the fiction-based content to find out everything perfect and happy in the end which is completely opposite from the real world.

This study reveals that the assumptions made are true to a large extent. The high use of social media affects the mental health and even relationships of the youth. Furthermore, the addiction of the social media has a direct relationship with mental health, including low self-esteem, sleep issues, and unrealistic body standards. Youth should be aware of these effects and must control their social media uses by setting screen time limits. Social media, no doubt is a great platform to interact with others but we all know that the excess use of everything is bad. This is the high time that youngsters should start paying attention on their mental health.

References

1. Panganiban, K. (2022, September 23). Social media and relationships. Choosing Therapy. Retrieved from <https://www.choosingtherapy.com/social-media-relationships/>
2. Bhaskar, D. (2024, January 13). Celebrities are moving away from social media. Dainik.
3. Special Report. (2023, January). The social dilemma: Social media and your mental health. Mass General Brigham, McLean. Retrieved from <https://www.mcleanhospital.org/essential/it-or-not-social-medias-affecting-your-mental-health>
4. Khalaf, A. M., Alubied, A. A., Khalaf, A. M., & Rifaey, A. A. (2023, August 5). The impact of social media on the mental health of adolescents and young adults: A systematic review. *Cureus*, 15(8). <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.43763>

5. Hunt, M. G. (2023, April 21). Feeling down? Social media may be to blame. Kaiser Permanente. Retrieved from <https://healthy.kaiserpermanente.org/health-wellness/healtharticle.feeling-down-social-media-may-blame>
6. Koehler, S. N., & Parrell, B. R. (2020, June). The impact of social media on mental health. California State University, Scholar Works. Retrieved from <https://scholarworks.lib.csusb.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2131&context=etd>
7. Bisma, A. (2022, June 20). The correlation between social media and mental health. Talkspace. Retrieved from <https://www.talkspace.com/blog/social-media-and-mental-health/>
8. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2023). Mental health. Retrieved from <https://www.cdc.gov/mentalhealth/learn/index.htm>
9. Khalaf, A. M., Alubied, A. A., Khalaf, A. M., & Rifaey, A. A. (2023, August 5). The impact of social media on the mental health of adolescents and young adults: A systematic review. *Cureus*, 15(8). <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.43763>
10. Buffer. (2022). Social media. Retrieved from <https://buffer.com/social-media-terms/social-media>
11. CliffsNotes. (2019). The negative impact of social media on mental health. Retrieved from <https://www.cliffsnotes.com/tutors-problems/English/50902299-This-essay-discusses-the-negative-impact-of-social-media-on-the/>
12. Zsila, Á., Reyes, M. E. S., & Article201, (2023). Impacts of social media on mental health. *BMC Psychology*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40359-023-01243-x>

